

INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASE AS AN AUTONOMOUS RISK FACTOR FOR METABOLIC-ASSOCIATED FATTY LIVER DISEASE*Petrova A.,**Slavcheva Grudeva-Trifonova L.**Clinic of Gastroenterology at University Hospital "St. Marina" Varna***ABSTRACT**

Inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) uniting Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis are chronic, immune-mediated conditions with multifactorial pathogenesis and recurrent course. Despite an increasing number of new therapeutic regimens, a significant proportion of patients fail to achieve deep clinical remission. This determines their high morbidity and disability, especially of young people, which contributes to the significant social and economic burden. On the other hand, with the introduction of new molecules and successful control of intestinal inflammation, obesity and metabolic syndrome in patients with IBD are reaching levels comparable to those in the general population.

Keywords: Inflammatory bowel disease; metabolic-associated fatty liver disease, obesity.

Introduction: Obesity is a chronic disease defined as the accumulation of excessive amounts of adipose tissue in the body. The global epidemic of overweight and obesity is slowly becoming a major health burden, leading to increased morbidity and mortality. It increases the risk of various diseases, including cardiovascular and oncological diseases, type 2 diabetes mellitus, sleep apnea, arthritis, and bronchial asthma. Overweight and obesity are among the most common nutritional disorders in patients with IBD. Patients with IBD and obesity experience accelerated clearance of immunomodulators and biological agents and poorer surgical outcomes compared to patients without obesity.

Materials and methods: We performed a systematic search in PubMed, Web of Science, Embase, and Scopus to identify available data reporting the association between IBD and MAFLD. We reported our experience regarding risk factors for MAFLD in patients with active ulcerative colitis.

Results: The environmental factors that play a role in inflammatory bowel disease are smoking, changes in the gut microbiome, changes in diet with increased consumption of linoleic acid, fats/animal proteins, and limited fiber intake. The Western diet promotes intestinal inflammation. Excess carbohydrates, polyunsaturated fatty acids, emulsifiers, and artificial sweeteners in food worsens intestinal inflammation and microbial dysbiosis, which is associated with obesity, metabolic-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD), and IBD. In some cases, IBS is accompanied by extreme weight loss and malabsorption syndrome, but recent studies indicate a significantly higher prevalence of NAFLD in these patients compared to the general population.

Liver diseases are common extraintestinal manifestations in IBD. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a proven predictor of increased transaminase activity in these patients. It is established as the most widespread liver disease in the world and a leading cause of mortality due to progression from steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, liver cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. About 10-20% of patients with NAFLD will develop cirrhosis. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease is defined as the accumulation of fat

in liver cells that cannot be attributed to excessive alcohol consumption.

Metabolism-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD) is a current nomenclature term that combines NAFLD and metabolic dysfunction. According to the authors, this new definition of MAFLD allows for the identification of a larger number of patients with metabolic syndrome who are at risk of developing cirrhosis and liver cancer. The diagnosis of MAFLD is based on histological, imaging, or serum biomarkers for hepatic steatosis, combined with one of the following parameters: overweight/obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, or evidence of metabolic dysregulation, regardless of alcohol consumption or other liver diseases. Metabolic risk abnormalities are: waist circumference ≥ 102 cm in men and 88 cm in women, blood pressure $\geq 130/85$ mmHg or medication, plasma triglycerides ≥ 150 mg/dl or medication, plasma HDL cholesterol < 40 mg/dL for men and < 50 mg/dL for women or medication, prediabetes and insulin resistance index ≥ 2.5 , C-reactive protein > 2 mg/L. From an epidemiological point of view, the prevalence of MAFLD varies between 26% and 39% in the general population, up to 42% in people with NAFLD and 50.7% in overweight/obese individuals.

The gut microbiota is an ecosystem made up of over 35,000 bacterial species that perform a bunch of functions, like metabolizing nutrients and drugs, antimicrobial protection, immune modulation, and keeping the gut barrier intact. Changes in the intestinal microflora determine the pathophysiological relationship between inflammatory bowel disease, obesity, and associated metabolic disorders. An unbalanced diet creates a disproportion of nutrients, which causes profound qualitative and quantitative changes in the intestinal microflora, disrupting the stability of the intestinal and vascular barrier, bacterial translocation, and steatotic liver disease. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is becoming established as a significant pathology, and its timely diagnosis, along with a change in the eating habits of patients with NAFLD, contributes to improving their metabolic profile. It often occurs asymptotically with abnormalities in liver and imaging tests. The semantic modification from "NAFLD" to "MAFLD" proposed by an international

expert group in 2020 emphasizes the role of metabolic factors in the etiology of the disease. In the latest published consensus reports, NAFLD has been replaced with the new term metabolic-associated fatty liver disease (MASLD). Several reasons motivated the experts to change the nomenclature, as discussed in detail in the article by Rinella et al. published in June 2023. They can be summarized as follows: to remove the stigma associated with the word "fatty" and to include at-risk patients with diabetes and those who consume alcohol above the threshold used to define NAFLD.

Patients with IBD often suffer from severe nutritional deficiencies due to malabsorption or short bowel syndrome. Parenteral nutrition is necessary during disease flare-ups. However, several potential side effects may occur, such as intestinal and liver damage through intestinal mucosal atrophy and progressive liver damage, which is often characterized by cholestasis in the early stages.

A number of studies have discussed the mechanisms underlying the relationship between MAFLD and IBD. Some of them indicate that the diagnosis of MAFLD in patients with IBD is mainly due to risk factors such as age, obesity, and type 2 diabetes, while others emphasize the importance of factors associated with inflammatory bowel disease itself—duration, severity of the disease, resections, dysbiosis, and drug-induced hepatotoxicity (Fig. 1). It is known that IBD increases the risk of early atherosclerosis even in young patients. Furthermore, MAFLD associated with IBD is a well-recognized but underdiagnosed process associated with cardiovascular risk. The presence of MAFLD may influence the choice of treatment for IBD. It is known that steatosis potentiates drug-induced liver disease, so patients with IBD and MAFLD undergoing immunosuppressive therapy are at higher risk of developing secondary liver damage. This highlights the importance of ultrasound examination of the liver in identifying at-risk patients.

Fig. 1. Specific factors in patients with IBD for the development of MAFLD, adapted from Maresca R, Mignini I, Varca S, et al. *Inflammatory Bowel Diseases and Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease: Piecing a Complex Puzzle Together. International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 2024

Between 2015 and 2023, 107 individuals with active ulcerative colitis were examined at the Gastroenterology Clinic of St. Marina University Hospital. The average age of the examined individuals was 36.2 ± 14.6 years, with a minimum age of 12 years and a maximum age of 71 years. Of these, 55 (51.4%) were men and 52 (48.6%) were women. One of the patients had confirmed type 2 diabetes. The body mass index was calculated for all individuals, with an average value of 25.4 ± 7.54 kg/m². This value is within the normal range according to the WHO. Although there is no evidence that being overweight changes the course of the disease, it is associated with adverse outcomes such as colon adenomas, increased cardiovascular mortality, and risk of thrombotic diseases.

Conclusion: Controlling intestinal inflammation modifies the risk of developing metabolic-associated fatty liver disease and its associated complications.

Treatment of patients with NAFLD should not be limited to the disease itself, but should also prevent the development of MAFLD by promoting a healthy lifestyle and appropriate diet.

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